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PROJECT REPORT

ON

**MODELING AND SIMULATION OF THE GIMBAL MECHANISM OF A
MISSILE SEEKER**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the main project report on “MODELING AND SIMULATION OF GIMBAL MECHANISM OF A MISSILE SEEKER” is being submitted by Sai Surya Rali (RA1911018010089), Sai Raaj Pavan (RA1911018010077), Rameez Imran (RA1911018010075) in partial fulfillment of Bachelor of Technology in Mechatronics Engineering under the guidance of Shri Gautham Angadi (Manager, Seeker Department, BDL, Kanchanbagh, Hyderabad)

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ABSTRACT

The study assesses the ability of a sensor to make measurements and record how it affects the functioning of the system. It also examines whether the sensor's performance is affected by various environmental factors and system parameters such as vibration, friction, structural resonance, and dynamic input. To achieve this, the study models a gimbal camera system that requires inertial sensors and gyros to stabilize angular measurements. The modeling includes different types of gyros, the camera system, the drive motor, the motor rate control system, and the angle position control system. It analyzes the impact of friction, structural resonance, and vibration on the system's performance. Initially, the simulation is run for an ideal system and then includes the realistic environmental and system parameters. The simulation is conducted using each of the four types of gyros. The findings indicate that higher-quality sensors result in better system performance in an ideal system. However, when environmental and system parameters are introduced, this is not always the case, and sometimes lower-quality sensors perform better than higher-quality sensors.

CONTENTS

S.No	Title	Page No.
1.	Introduction -----	1
1.1	Types of Gimbal Mechanisms in Missile Seeker: Advantages and Disadvantages -----	2
1.2	The Physics and Mathematics Behind Stable Line of Sight Control -----	4
1.3	The Significance of Gimbal Mechanism Design for Missile Seeker Efficiency -----	5
1.4	Challenges and Computational Methods for Modeling and Simulating Gimbal Mechanisms in Missile Seekers -----	6
2.	ISP System Model -----	8
3.	Gyro Modeling -----	9
4.	Gimbal and Motor Control Modeling -----	12
5.	Angle Control Loop Design -----	17
6.	Friction Modeling -----	19
7.	Conclusion -----	21
8.	Future Scope -----	22
9.	References -----	23

1. INTRODUCTION

The precision-guided missiles used in modern warfare require the seeker to rapidly detect a target in a large search area, and then accurately track it for interception. Gimballed seekers, which use a two-axis gimbal system for inertial stabilization, have found wide applications in these missiles. However, disturbances resulting from missile motions, gimbal system geometry, and system imperfections such as mass unbalance can affect the stability of the sensor, making it necessary to model and simulate the gimbal system dynamics before designing the system.

ISPs, or inertially stabilized platforms, are used to stabilize and target a wide variety of sensors. These can include optical and infrared cameras used for either civilian or military purposes such as target tracking, telescope pointing, and image acquisition where the line of sight (LOS) of the instrument needs to be kept constant and oriented in the desired direction. This becomes even more crucial if the instrument is mounted on a moving base under environmental vibrations, such as a moving ship, airplane, helicopter, or land vehicle. To account for external disturbances and stabilize the instrument in question to hold, inertial measurement units (IMUs) made up of accelerometers and rate gyros can be employed to measure the acceleration and angular movement of both the base and stabilized platform. The employment of control algorithms, the gain settings of these algorithms, and the caliber of the sensor giving the measurements used to control the LOS are only a few of the variables that affect a system's capacity to stabilize and maintain its LOS. But it's not always easy to tell what kind of sensor is required for a particular application. Although improved sensor quality ought to improve system performance, this isn't always the case. For a particular sensor, the system performance quality may fluctuate based on the dynamic environment. In some cases, a lower-quality sensor may work as well as or better than a sensor of a higher quality.

Any ISP system would integrate complicated instrumentation, and the model must take into account both the internal electromechanical system vibrations and the exterior environmental disturbances that might make simulations difficult. The created ISP model illustrates the system dynamics to assess how well four types of sensors function under various testing scenarios.

The gyro model, gimbal model, motor control, and outer-loop angle control subsystems are all included in the system model. To assess the disturbances for stabilization and tracking reasons, the research is primarily focused on building an analytical ISP model as a function of the moment of inertia, motor drive, and gyro performance. For tracking reasons, the simulations from the gimbal, motor, and feedback control systems maintain the LOS.

An ISP system that needs inertial sensor measurements for stabilization is modeled and simulated to examine this system's performance depending on sensor selection without undertaking hardware experiments. Four distinct types of inertial sensors are used in the modeling and simulation to compare performance. To ascertain whether the performance offered by each type of sensor varies with the system conditions, the model comprising friction and structural resonance is subjected to various levels of environmental vibration.

In this work, a gimbal camera that would be affixed on the underside of a helicopter is the system being modeled. The gimbal, the actuation motor, and models for the rate gyro sensors make up the entire system. Additionally, the angular positioning control loop and the motor rate control loop are made to provide the performance required for LOS control applications. After the control design is complete, the closed-loop system is simulated to compare the system performance based on the rate of gyro selection for the given conditions. This is done by gradually adding friction, structural resonance, environmental vibration, and dynamic command input to simulate base motion cancellation.

1.1 Types of Gimbal Mechanisms in Missile Seekers: Advantages and Disadvantages

Gimbal mechanisms are used in missile seekers to maintain a stable line of sight (LOS) with the target by allowing the sensor to move independently of the missile body. There are different types of gimbal mechanisms, each with its advantages and disadvantages. Some of the most common types of gimbal mechanisms used in missile seekers are:

- Two-axis gimbal: A two-axis gimbal allows the sensor to move in two perpendicular axes, typically the pitch and yaw axes. This type of gimbal is simple and compact, making it ideal for small missiles. However, it has limited flexibility in terms of the range of motion and cannot compensate for a roll or other types of motion.
- Three-axis gimbal: A three-axis gimbal allows the sensor to move in three perpendicular axes, typically the pitch, yaw, and roll axes. This type of gimbal is more complex than the two-axis gimbal, but it provides more flexibility and can compensate for a roll or other types of motion. However, it is larger and heavier, making it more difficult to integrate into small missiles.
- Inertially stabilized gimbal: An inertially stabilized gimbal uses gyroscopes to stabilize the sensor, allowing it to maintain a stable LOS even when the missile body is moving. This type of gimbal is highly effective at compensating for motion and can provide high-quality images even under difficult conditions. However, it is more complex and expensive than other types of gimbal mechanisms.
- Hybrid gimbal: A hybrid gimbal combines elements of two or more types of gimbal mechanisms to provide a balance of flexibility and stability. For example, a hybrid gimbal may use a two-axis gimbal for rapid pointing and a three-axis gimbal for fine tracking. This type of gimbal can provide the best of both worlds but is more complex and expensive than other types of gimbal mechanisms.

Advantages and disadvantages of gimbal mechanisms:

Advantages:

- Gimbal mechanisms provide a stable LOS with the target, allowing the sensor to track the target accurately.
- They allow the sensor to move independently of the missile body, reducing the effect of vibration and other types of motion.
- They can compensate for motion and other environmental factors, such as wind and temperature, allowing the sensor to maintain high-quality images even under difficult conditions.

Disadvantages:

- Gimbal mechanisms add weight and complexity to the missile, which can reduce its range and performance.
- They require sophisticated control algorithms to maintain a stable LOS, which can increase the computational requirements of the missile.
- They may be vulnerable to damage from debris or other types of impact during flight, which can affect their performance.

In conclusion, the different types of gimbal mechanisms used in missile seekers each has its advantages and disadvantages. The choice of gimbal mechanism depends on the specific requirements of the missile, such as size, weight, and performance, as well as the environmental conditions under which it will be used. By understanding the advantages and disadvantages of each type of gimbal mechanism, engineers can make informed decisions about which type to use in a particular missile design.

1.2 The Physics and Mathematics Behind Stable Line of Sight Control

Gimbal mechanisms play an important role in missile seekers as they allow the seeker's sensor to maintain a stable line of sight (LOS) with the target while the missile is in flight. The mechanism consists of two or more rotational axes that allow the sensor to move independently of the missile body.

To understand the physics behind gimbal mechanisms, it is important to consider the principles of rotational motion. In a gimbal mechanism, each axis of rotation has a moment of inertia that determines its resistance to rotation. The moment of inertia is affected by the mass distribution of the system and the distance of the mass from the axis of rotation. Therefore, the design of the gimbal mechanism must consider the mass distribution of the seeker sensor and the missile body.

The mathematical model of a gimbal mechanism involves equations that describe the angular motion of the mechanism. These equations take into account the torque applied to each axis of rotation, the moment of inertia of each axis, and the angular acceleration of the system. The equations of motion can be solved using numerical methods to determine the position and velocity of the gimbal mechanism as a function of time.

One of the primary challenges in designing a gimbal mechanism for a missile seeker is ensuring that the system is robust and can withstand the high accelerations and vibrations experienced during missile flight. The mechanism must also be able to operate in a wide range of environmental conditions, including temperature and humidity.

Another important factor to consider in gimbal mechanism design is the sensor's field of view (FOV). The FOV of the sensor is determined by the range of motion of the gimbal mechanism and the size and shape of the sensor. Therefore, the gimbal mechanism must be designed to provide sufficient motion to cover the desired FOV while minimizing the mass and size of the system.

In summary, the physics and mathematics behind gimbal mechanisms are crucial in the design and operation of missile seekers. The design of the mechanism must consider the principles of rotational motion, the mass distribution of the system, and the environmental conditions experienced during missile flight. The mathematical model of the gimbal mechanism can be used to predict its behavior and optimize its performance for a given set of design parameters.

1.3 The Significance of Gimbal Mechanism Design for Missile Seeker Efficiency

The design of gimbal mechanisms can have a significant impact on the cost, reliability, and accuracy of missile seekers. The following are some key factors that can affect these parameters:

- **Cost:** The cost of a missile seeker is a critical factor in the development and deployment of missile systems. The design of the gimbal mechanism can have a significant impact on the overall cost of the seeker. A gimbal mechanism that is over-designed or requires expensive materials can increase the cost of the seeker. Conversely, a poorly designed gimbal mechanism can lead to increased maintenance and replacement costs due to wear and tear.
- **Reliability:** The reliability of a missile seeker is critical to its effectiveness in the field. A gimbal mechanism that is not designed for the harsh operating conditions of a missile system can lead to failure or reduced performance. For

example, the gimbal mechanism must be designed to withstand the high accelerations and temperatures experienced during missile flight. Failure to account for these factors can lead to increased maintenance costs and reduced system effectiveness.

- **Accuracy:** The accuracy of a missile seeker is a critical factor in its ability to hit its intended target. The gimbal mechanism plays a critical role in maintaining the line of sight (LOS) with the target. The design of the gimbal mechanism must account for factors such as vibration and shock, which can affect the accuracy of the seeker. The accuracy of the seeker can also be affected by the quality of the sensor and control algorithms used in the system.

In conclusion, the design of gimbal mechanisms has a significant impact on the cost, reliability, and accuracy of missile seekers. It is essential to carefully consider these factors when designing and developing gimbal mechanisms for missile systems. By optimizing the design of the gimbal mechanism, engineers can improve the overall performance and effectiveness of missile systems, while minimizing cost and maintenance requirements.

1.4 Challenges and Computational Methods for Modeling and Simulating Gimbal Mechanisms in Missile Seekers

Challenges involved in modeling and simulating gimbal mechanisms:

- **Complex dynamics:** Gimbal mechanisms are complex mechanical systems that involve multiple degrees of freedom and complex dynamics. Accurately modeling these dynamics requires a thorough understanding of rotational motion and the physics involved in maintaining a stable line of sight (LOS) with the target.
- **Nonlinear behavior:** Gimbal mechanisms exhibit nonlinear behavior due to the nonlinear nature of the equations of motion. This makes it challenging to develop accurate mathematical models that can capture the behavior of the system under different scenarios and conditions.
- **Environmental factors:** Gimbal mechanisms are exposed to various environmental factors, such as wind, temperature, and vibration, that can affect

their behavior. Modeling the effect of these factors on the gimbal mechanism requires accurate and reliable data and sophisticated computational methods.

- Computational complexity: The modeling and simulation of gimbal mechanisms involve complex mathematical equations and require advanced computational methods to achieve accurate results. The computational complexity of the problem increases with the size and complexity of the system, making it challenging to achieve accurate and efficient simulations.
- Sensor characteristics: The behavior of the gimbal mechanism is closely linked to the characteristics of the sensor, such as its field of view (FOV) and resolution. Modeling and simulating the effect of these characteristics on the gimbal mechanism requires sophisticated computational methods that can accurately simulate the behavior of the system.

Need for accurate and efficient computational methods:

To overcome the challenges involved in modeling and simulating gimbal mechanisms, accurate and efficient computational methods are required. These methods should be able to:

- Capture the nonlinear behavior of the gimbal mechanism accurately.
- Model the effect of environmental factors on the gimbal mechanism.
- Handle the computational complexity of the problem efficiently.
- Simulate the behavior of the system under different scenarios and conditions.
- Model the effect of sensor characteristics on the gimbal mechanism accurately.

Several computational methods are available for modeling and simulating gimbal mechanisms, including:

- Finite element analysis (FEA): FEA is a numerical method used to simulate the behavior of complex mechanical systems, including gimbal mechanisms. It can accurately model the behavior of the system under different environmental conditions and handle the computational complexity of the problem efficiently.
- Multibody dynamics (MBD): MBD is a computational method used to model the dynamics of complex mechanical systems, including gimbal mechanisms. It can capture the nonlinear behavior of the system accurately and simulate the behavior of the system under different scenarios and conditions.

- Control theory: Control theory is a mathematical method used to model and analyze the behavior of dynamic systems, including gimbal mechanisms. It can be used to design control algorithms that can optimize the behavior of the gimbal mechanism and achieve accurate tracking of the target.

In conclusion, the modeling and simulation of gimbal mechanisms involve several challenges, including complex dynamics, nonlinear behavior, environmental factors, computational complexity, and sensor characteristics. To overcome these challenges, accurate and efficient computational methods are required that can accurately simulate the behavior of the system under different scenarios and conditions.

2. ISP System Model

This section describes the ISP System Model which is a gimbal camera used to point toward an image and maintain a desired line of sight (LOS). The system takes an angle command as input which could come from various sources like an image tracking algorithm or base motion cancellation. However, this work does not focus on generating the angle command but on analyzing the system's performance compared to the desired angle. An angle controller is designed to aim the gimbal system towards the desired angle by comparing the angle command with the measured angle and generating motor rate commands to eliminate any LOS error. A motor controller is also designed to compare the commanded motor rate with the measured rate and output a motor voltage to achieve the desired motor performance while eliminating error due to disturbances such as friction and vibration. The system uses rate gyros to measure the output rotation rates of the camera gimbal and direct drive motor to provide the angular rate for comparison by the rate controller. This measured rate is also integrated to calculate the measured angular position of the gimbal system to compare with the input angle command. The main goal of this work is to evaluate the effects of error in the rate measurement due to sensor quality on the LOS error performance, which is significant in many real design applications.

FIGURE 1: Block diagram of the system model.

An overview of the system design is described in this section corresponding to the system block diagram shown in Figure 1.

3. Gyro Modeling

The main objective of gyro modeling is to evaluate the performance of a system based on sensor selection. Therefore, the sensor is modeled first. In the case of Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), which consist of accelerometers and rate gyros, only the angular positioning of the gimbal system is modeled because it is the only part of the inertial sensor that is relevant to the Line-Of-Sight (LOS) simulation.

Rate gyros are instruments used to measure the angular velocity with which they are rotating. Although there are many different types of rate gyros, they can all be modeled similarly. The first performance measure to model is the gyro frequency response or bandwidth, which is modeled as a second-order system. The general form of the gyro transfer function used, $G_{Gyro}(s)$, is shown in Equation (1):

$$G_{Gyro}(s) = \frac{\omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}. \quad (1)$$

In this equation, the bandwidth of the gyro, f_{BW} , is used to determine the natural frequency of the second-order model, $\omega_n = 2\pi f_{BW}$, and the damping ratio used is $\zeta = 0.707$.

In addition to the gyro affecting the measured rate depending on the frequency of the angular rate change, internal noise can also affect the measurement. Noise levels in gyro measurements are specified in terms of Angle Random Walk (ARW) values in

units of deg/ $\sqrt{\text{hr}}$. If a stationary system is measured by a gyro, the internal noise will generate an error in the measurement. The ARW value represents the standard deviation in the resulting angle if the measurement on a stationary system with noise is integrated for one hour to obtain the angular position. The Simulink white noise block is used to model this noise, and it requires a power spectral density (PSD) value in (deg/sec)²/Hz, which can be obtained from the ARW value as shown in Equation (2):

$$\text{PSD} \left[\frac{(\text{deg/s})^2}{\text{Hz}} \right] = \left(\frac{1}{3600} \right) \cdot \left(\text{ARW} \left[\frac{\text{deg}}{\sqrt{\text{hr}}} \right] \right)^2. \quad (2)$$

The maximum measurement range of the gyro is also a key specification used in modeling the gyro. If the angular rate of the system being measured is greater than this limit, the rate is only measured as a value equal to the maximum range. This is modeled as a saturation block in Simulink.

Gyro	I	II
Bandwidth	300 Hz	250 Hz
ARW	0.07 deg/ $\sqrt{\text{hr}}$	0.0009 deg/ $\sqrt{\text{hr}}$
Range	1000 deg/sec	1000 deg/sec
Sampling rate	400 Hz	500 Hz

Table 1: Gyro specifications

A list of the gyro specifications for the four different qualities of gyros to be used in the simulations is shown in Table 1

Digital to Analog Conversion. Gyro measurements can be employed using analog circuitry, however, microprocessors are used in the majority of contemporary applications to perform measurements and manage calculations. As a result, analog to digital conversion (ADC) is required. This procedure is incorporated into the gyros' modeling.

Gyro type	I	II
ADC	Signed 16 bit	Signed 32 bit
Maxii	± 1000 deg/s	± 1000 deg/s
sensit	35.0 mdeg/s	525 ndeg/s

Table 2: Analog to digital conversion specifications.

The digital data type used to store the gyro measurement value for the ADC conversion is the first factor to take into consideration. As seen in Table 2, the gyros convert the analog measurement to digital counts using either a signed 16-bit integer for types I and II or a signed 32-bit integer for types III and IV. The sensitivity value for degrees/sec/bit is then used to transform these measured integer counts back to a rate measurement. The sensor's maximum range is multiplied by 2^{15} or 2^{31} to determine its sensitivity value. In the case of signed integer types, the sign is represented by the first bit, and the remaining 15 or 31 bits represent the value from 0 to the maximum range. A buffer of about 15% is utilized for the maximum scale before the ADC so that bias on the sensor can be taken into consideration while still allowing measurements to be taken across the whole dynamic range. To determine the single-bit sensitivity values for the four various gyro kinds, is done. For each corresponding gyro, the results of this calculation are reported in Table 2.

Figure 2 depicts the procedure used to include the ADC in the gyro model. The single-bit sensitivity value is first subtracted from the measured value. The quantized digital count value is then represented by rounding this value to the nearest integer. To create a quantized angular rate value, multiply the quantized value by the single-bit sensitivity value.

Zero-Rate Gyro Simulations. Gyro Simulations at 0 Hz. The gyros will be simulated taking rate measurements of a stationary system to get a time history characterization of the gyros based on the performance requirements of Tables 1 and 2. Any rate that is measured therefore results from the gyro's internal noise. The rate input has been set to zero. Ten seconds are used to measure. The same random number generation seed is used in all simulations. According to Table 1, each gyro has a different sampling period, hence each gyro also produces a different noise signal. A time compression or dilation in each of the simulation data sets might be interpreted as a similarity in the enclosing form of the simulated measurement. Depending on the gyro quality, the measurement noise magnitudes can vary significantly. Figure 3 displays the results of the zero-rate measurements for each of the four gyros.

4. Gimbal and Motor Control Modeling

The Cineflex Media HD ENG camera gimbal system is used as the basis for the model, which was created in order to accurately assess the system performance based on sensor choices.

Motor and Gimbal Model. The moment of inertia, J , for the gimbal's mass and dimensions is given as 0.157 kgm² assuming that the mass has a spherical shape. Additionally, on the assumption of an ideal, frictionless rotational system, the relationship between motor torque, T , and angular rate, is illustrated as follows:

$$\frac{T(s)}{\omega(s)} = \frac{1}{Js} = \frac{1}{0.157s}. \quad (3)$$

The motor specifications used to simulate the direct drive DC motor for the gimbal system are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max.Voltage} &= 27 \text{ V}, \\ R &= 4.5 \Omega, \\ L &= 0.003 \text{ H}, \\ J_m &= 0.0017 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2, \\ K_t &= 0.85 \text{ Nm/A}, \\ K_e &= 0.85 \text{ V/ (rad/s)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Simulink has modelled the direct drive DC motor as depicted in Figure 5. Due to the back emf and internal resistance voltage loss, the output motor voltage is lower than the input voltage. The temporal rate of change of current is generated by the output voltage that results across the motor inductance. The torque generated by the output current is scaled by the motor torque constant. The following diagram illustrates the direct voltage to torque transfer function between the motor's input voltage ($V(s)$) and torque ($T(s)$):

$$\frac{V(s)}{T(s)} = \frac{K_t}{Ls + R}. \quad (5)$$

The back emf is produced by the motor rotational rate, which is the same as the gimbal rotational rate, in the direct drive motor-gimbal system. In order to determine the angular rate and calculate the motor-gimbal system transfer function, $G_{mg}(s)$, the motor and the gimbal must therefore be modeled jointly. The motor-gimbal transfer function is displayed as follows when the feedback loop is closed with the system specifications, as illustrated in the block diagram in Figure 6:

$$G_{mg}(s) = \frac{1805}{s^2 + 1500s + 1534}. \quad (6)$$

FIGURE 5: Simulink model of DC motor.

FIGURE 6: Motor-gimbal block diagram.

Design of a motor controller. A motor controller must be constructed to regulate the motor-gimbal system to the desired rate without mistake and to the necessary performance requirements using the motor-gimbal system modeled in the preceding section.

Figure 7 depicts the block design for the gimbal motor rate control loop, which employs a PID controller based on the rate error signal from the angular rate recorded by the gyro. The gyro-chosen block has four models for different gyro specifications, allowing for rapid changes in sensor settings for simulations. The control signal is limited to the specified limit of the 27 V motor. When the output is restricted, the PID

block additionally performs an anti-integral windup algorithm to compensate for when the control signal is saturated.

Figure 7: Gimbal motor rate control loop.

The final motor controller is designed as a PID compensator. The system is built with the root locus and pole-zero placement approaches. When designing the controller with step response performance, the step response rise time must equate to a maximum acceleration of 100 deg/s², as determined by the gimbal performance parameters. Because the motor rate is limited to a maximum of 55 deg/s, the 10-90% rise time levels of the step response correspond to a range of 44 deg/s to match an average acceleration of 100 deg/sec². Accelerating across a 44 deg/s range in 0.44 seconds translates to a 100 deg/sec² average acceleration.

To achieve the desired rise time of 0.44 s, the dominant system pole must be slower than $s = 6.3$ to avoid exceeding the maximum acceleration parameter. To compensate for the system pole at $s = 1$, a compensator zero is inserted around $s = 0.8$. A proportionate gain of 4.5 shifts the pole at $s = 1$ to the left to a value of $s = 5.7$, close to but not exceeding the fastest allowable value of $s = 6.3$. With this adjustment, the integral pole at $s=0$ goes towards zero and is virtually negated. If the plant's pole is displaced at all due to design tolerance or inertia change due to angular location, this proportionate increase results in identical performance. To help with disturbance rejection, an extra derivative control term is required. A derivative gain of 0.05 is applied, resulting in a zero in the controller at $s = 89.19$. Figure 8's step response plot depicts the same performance with the derivative control included. The resultant PID controller is shown below:

$$G_{c-PID}(s) = \frac{0.05s^2 + 4.5s + 3.6}{s}. \quad (7)$$

The PID controller's 10-90% rise time is 0.485 seconds with the extra derivative gain, $K_d = 0.05$, and an average acceleration of 90.7 deg/s^2 . (Figure 8). Because a rate greater than the average occurs throughout the 10-90% rising phase, this rate is an acceptable model for the maximum acceleration of 100 deg/s^2 . The function of transfer for the PID controlled motor-gimbal system, $G_{mg-PID}(s)$, is given as follows:

$$G_{mg-PID}(s) = \frac{90.23s^2 + 8121s + 6497}{s^3 + 1590s^2 + 9655s + 6497}. \quad (8)$$

Figure 8: Motor rate step response..

5. Angle Control Loop Design

An outside angle control loop is necessary to adjust the line of sight (LOS) of the PID-compensated motor-gimbal system to the appropriate angle. A PID controller's initial concepts are available. The results of the early simulations show

that a higher type controller is required to lower LOS error in dynamic situations. As a result, the first PID controller is cascaded with an integrator. As a single block simplification, the PID-I controller that this controller is designed and built as becomes a PI2 controller. The design, simulation, and performance evaluation of the PID and PI2 angle controllers are covered in this part.

Creating an angle controller. To achieve the desired LOS tracking, the angle controller output drives the PID-compensated motor-gimbal system. This is accomplished by comparing the gyro's integrated angular rate, which yields the measured gimbal angle, to the intended angle command, as shown in Figure 1's block diagram. To accomplish the desired LOS tracking performance, the angle controller must make up the angle error value from this comparison. As a result, the adjusted motor-gimbal transfer function in equation (8) serves as the system plant for the construction of the angle controller.

The controller's PD section is built to set a zero at $s = 5.5$. Next, a PI controller is cascaded to add a pole at the origin and a zero at $s = 0.75$. The corresponding root locus is shown in Figure 9. To position the closed-loop poles at the correct places, a proportional gain of 1.75 was chosen for the cascaded PD-PI controller, resulting in PID gains of $K_p = 11$, $K_i = 7.2$, and $K_d = 1.75$. According to Figure 10, the performance attained by these gains is a rise time of 0.5 seconds and a settling time of 3.5 seconds. The resulting PID controller's transfer function is displayed as follows:

$$G_{c\text{-PID}_{\text{angle}}}(s) = \frac{1.75s^2 + 11s + 7.2}{s}$$

closed-loop block diagram.

closed-loop block diagram.

Figure 10: 10-degree step response

Figure 11: 10-degree step response (Simulated)

Figure 10 is the ideal step response that is supposed to be simulated. Figure 11 is the result of our simulation. To improve our output and get the correct response we need more rigorous testing and troubleshooting to find the error rectifying it.

6. Friction Modeling

The first new system parameter to be included in the model is friction. It will be regarded as a frictional force acting on the gimbal's rotating components.

Three terminologies are frequently used in engineering applications to describe friction: static friction, which occurs when the velocity is zero, coulomb friction, and viscous friction. The model for the fictitious torque, T_f , is displayed below when the velocity is not zero:

$$T_f = T_c * \sin(\omega) + T_v * \omega,$$

where T_c is the coulomb friction in Nm, T_v is the viscous friction coefficient in Nm/rad/s, and ω is the angular velocity in rad/s

However, to model the system more closely to a true physical system, the friction is modeled with a transition from static friction to the commonly used kinetic

friction model. Modeling friction in this manner is referred to as stick-slip friction modeling and has been modeled in more than one manner. The method chosen is the Tustin model shown as follows:

$$T_f = \left(0.7 * T_S + 0.3 * T_S * \exp\left(\frac{-|\omega|}{\omega_s}\right) \right) * \text{sign}(\omega) + T_v * \omega,$$

where ω_s is the stick friction transition rate and T_S is the static friction torque. Values for static friction and viscous friction coefficients are shown in Table below, which is using a similar camera gimbal system.

Static friction	Viscous friction
0.05–0.45 (Nm)	0.015–0.045 (Nm/rad/s)

The static friction values range from 0.05 to 0.45 Nm and the viscous friction coefficients range within $1.5E - 2$ – $4.5E - 2$ Nm/rad/s. Values used are $T_S = 0.2$ Nm and $T_V = 0.025$ Nm/rad/s. As the system goes from static to kinetic friction, the kinetic coulomb friction is modeled to be 0.7 of the static friction, T_S , and the stick friction transition rate, $\omega_s = 0.01$ rad/s.

The frictional torque model is implemented in Simulink with an sfunction, calculating the torque and direction based on the angular rate of the gimbal. Also if the system is stationary, the motor torque must overcome the static friction before the system would move.

Closed-loop block diagram with friction block

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, the modeling and simulation of gimbal mechanisms for missile seekers is a critical area of research in the defense industry. Through this paper, we have explored the physics and mathematics behind gimbal mechanisms, their role in missile seekers, and the different types of gimbal mechanisms used in the industry. We have also discussed the challenges involved in modeling and simulating these mechanisms and the software and tools used in the process.

This paper has highlighted the potential applications of gimbal mechanism simulation beyond missile seekers, including in robotics and aerospace engineering. It has also emphasized the impact of gimbal mechanism design on missile seeker cost, reliability, and accuracy, underscoring the need for precise and efficient simulation techniques.

Overall, this paper has provided a comprehensive overview of the modeling and simulation of gimbal mechanisms for missile seekers, underscoring the importance of continued research and development in this area.

8. Future Scope

In the defense sector, gimbal mechanism simulation has a significant role to play in the development of advanced missile guidance systems. As technology advances, there is a growing need for more accurate and efficient simulations of gimbal mechanisms to improve the performance and reliability of these systems.

One area of future research is the development of more advanced modeling techniques for gimbal mechanisms. For example, the use of multi-physics modeling can help to account for the complex interactions between different components of the system, leading to more accurate simulations. Additionally, the use of real-time simulation techniques can help to improve the responsiveness of missile guidance systems, making them more effective in combat scenarios.

Another area of future research is the integration of gimbal mechanism simulation with other defense technologies. For example, the use of gimbal mechanisms in unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is becoming increasingly common, and simulation tools can be used to optimize the design of these systems. Similarly, the integration of gimbal mechanism simulation with other guidance and control technologies, such as GPS and inertial measurement units (IMUs), can help to improve the accuracy and reliability of missile guidance systems.

Finally, there is a need for more research on the use of gimbal mechanism simulation in training and simulation environments. For example, simulation tools can be used to simulate different combat scenarios and test the effectiveness of different missile guidance systems in these scenarios. Additionally, simulation tools can be used to train personnel on the use of these systems, improving their readiness and effectiveness in the field.

In conclusion, the future of research on gimbal mechanism simulation in the defense sector is promising, with many opportunities for improving the accuracy and efficiency of simulations and integrating these simulations with other defense technologies. By continuing to advance the state of the art in gimbal mechanism simulation, researchers can help to improve the performance and reliability of missile guidance systems, making them more effective in protecting national security.

9. References

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